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Assessing The Role of Digital Finance in Addressing Poverty and Financial Exclusion Among Vulnerable Groups in Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the role of digital finance in addressing poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria. Using a mixed-method approach, data were collected from 385 households through structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Descriptive statistics, logistic regression, and odds ratio analyses were employed to examine the determinants of digital finance adoption and the barriers affecting its utilization. The findings reveal that household digital literacy, access to internet and mobile networks, education, and trust in digital finance institutions significantly increase the likelihood of adopting digital financial services. Conversely, perceived high costs and regulatory concerns were found to hinder adoption, particularly among vulnerable households. The study also demonstrates that digital finance adoption positively influences access to financial services and employment opportunities, contributing to poverty reduction and economic empowerment. Despite these benefits, disparities in infrastructure, digital literacy, and socio-economic vulnerability limit the full potential of digital financial inclusion. The study concludes that digital finance is a critical tool for fostering inclusive economic development in urban Nigerian contexts, provided that complementary interventions, such as digital literacy programs, affordable service offerings, and trust-building initiatives, are implemented. These findings have important implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and development stakeholders seeking to enhance financial inclusion and poverty alleviation through digital innovations.

Keywords: Digital Finance, Financial Inclusion, Poverty Alleviation, Vulnerable Groups

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Financial exclusion and poverty remain critical development challenges in Nigeria, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations such as low-income households, women, youth, and those with limited educational attainment (Nejo et al., 2025; Oyinloye et al., 2025; Ismail et al., 2025). In

developing economies, digital finance—which includes mobile banking, digital payments, and fintech solutions—has emerged as a promising mechanism to expand access to formal financial services and reduce barriers to economic participation (Enebeli-Uzor & Mukhtar, 2023; Abdullahi *et al.*, 2024; Magaji *et al.*, 2025a). Digital finance can potentially provide underserved groups with affordable, secure, and convenient financial tools, helping to bridge longstanding gaps in traditional financial service delivery (Magaji & Ahmad, 2024). However, the extent to which digital finance actually mitigates poverty and financial exclusion in specific urban contexts like Abuja requires empirical scrutiny.

The expansion of digital financial services across Nigeria reflects broader global trends toward digitalisation and financial innovation. Digital finance is widely understood as the provision of financial products and services through digital channels such as mobile money, agency banking, and online platforms, which reduce reliance on physical banking infrastructure (Eke *et al.*, 2023). Studies have documented that digital financial inclusion positively influences economic outcomes by increasing access to credit, savings, and payment systems, particularly among low-income and previously unbanked populations (Hussaini & Umar Dikko, 2025; Igwe *et al.*, 2021). This expansion is particularly salient in urban areas like Abuja, where mobile phone penetration and digital connectivity are relatively high compared to rural regions, offering a unique opportunity to assess the socio-economic impact of digital finance.

Despite the promise of digital financial services, significant obstacles constrain their ability to fully address financial exclusion and poverty. Infrastructure limitations—such as inconsistent internet connectivity, electricity shortages, and gaps in digital literacy—continue to impede widespread adoption among vulnerable groups. Moreover, recent research suggests that while digital finance enhances access to financial services, systemic barriers persist, including affordability challenges, limited awareness of digital solutions, and socio-cultural factors affecting trust and usage. These challenges underscore the need for context-specific investigations that examine how digital financial services perform in real-world settings like Abuja and whether they translate into tangible improvements in economic inclusion.

Empirical evidence from Nigeria and other developing contexts further supports the role of digital finance in poverty reduction, yet highlights mixed outcomes that depend on enabling conditions. Research across Sub-Saharan Africa shows that digital financial services can contribute to economic inclusion by increasing account ownership and facilitating financial transactions, although obstacles such as the digital divide and regulatory weaknesses may dampen the full potential of these technologies (Opoku-Okuampa, 2024). In Nigeria, targeted studies on digital finance and its relationship with financial inclusion reveal positive correlations, suggesting that digital finance expansion can reduce exclusion gaps, yet also call for enhanced infrastructure and policy support to maximise socio-economic benefits.

Given these dynamics, assessing the role of digital finance in addressing poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja is both timely and necessary. Such an assessment can inform policymakers, financial service providers, and development practitioners on how to tailor digital finance strategies that are inclusive, equitable, and responsive to the needs of marginalised populations. This study therefore contributes to the growing body of knowledge on digital financial inclusion by focusing on the lived experiences and financial outcomes of vulnerable groups in Nigeria's capital, providing evidence that can support inclusive financial policy design and implementation.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conceptual Issues

2.1.1 Digital Finance

Digital finance refers to the delivery of financial products and services through digital channels such as mobile phones, computers, the internet, and electronic cards (Eke *et al.*, 2022). It encompasses services

including mobile money, digital payments, online banking, fintech platforms, and agency banking, which reduce dependence on physical financial infrastructure (World Bank, 2022). Digital finance has gained prominence in developing economies due to its potential to lower transaction costs, expand outreach to unbanked populations, and improve efficiency in financial service delivery. Empirical studies indicate that digital finance enhances access to savings, credit, and payment systems, particularly for low-income individuals and small businesses, thereby contributing to broader financial inclusion and economic participation (Ozili, 2018). In Nigeria, the rapid expansion of fintech and mobile money services underscores the growing relevance of digital finance as a development tool.

2.1.2 Poverty

Poverty is a multidimensional condition characterized not only by low income but also by deprivation in basic needs such as food, shelter, education, healthcare, and access to economic opportunities (Jafaru et al., 2025; Shaba et al., 2018; Magaji et al., 2025b). The World Bank (2023) defines poverty as the inability to attain a minimum standard of living, often measured using income thresholds such as the international poverty line. Beyond monetary measures, poverty also includes social exclusion, vulnerability to economic shocks, and limited access to productive resources (Magaji, 2007; Musa et al., 2024). In developing countries like Nigeria, poverty remains pervasive despite economic growth, with urban poverty increasingly affecting residents of cities such as Abuja. Scholars argue that addressing poverty requires inclusive economic systems that improve access to financial services, employment opportunities, and social protection mechanisms (UNDP, 2022).

2.1.3 Financial Exclusion

Financial exclusion refers to the inability or limited ability of individuals or groups to access and use formal financial services such as bank accounts, credit facilities, insurance, and payment systems. This exclusion may result from factors including low income, lack of identification, geographical barriers, high transaction costs, and limited financial literacy (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022). Financial exclusion restricts individuals' capacity to save securely, invest productively, and manage financial risks, thereby reinforcing cycles of poverty and inequality (Sanusi et al., 2025). In Nigeria, despite improvements in financial infrastructure, a significant proportion of the population—particularly low-income earners and informal sector workers—remains excluded from formal financial systems. Digital finance is increasingly viewed as a viable solution to reducing financial exclusion by offering more accessible and flexible financial products.

2.1.4 Vulnerable Groups

Vulnerable groups are populations that face heightened risks of social, economic, and financial marginalisation due to structural, demographic, or socio-economic disadvantages (Abiola et al., 2025; Olusola et al., 2025). These groups commonly include women, youth, the elderly, persons with disabilities, internally displaced persons, and low-income households (United Nations, 2021). Vulnerability is often exacerbated by limited access to education, employment, healthcare, and financial services, making these groups more susceptible to poverty and economic shocks. In urban centres such as Abuja, vulnerable groups frequently operate within the informal economy and lack access to formal banking services. Studies suggest that inclusive digital financial solutions can help mitigate vulnerabilities by improving access to income-generating opportunities, social transfers, and financial safety nets (Klapper & Singer, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Financial Intermediation Theory

The Financial Intermediation Theory is highly relevant to this study as it explains how financial institutions and mechanisms reduce transaction costs and information asymmetry between savers and borrowers, thereby enhancing access to financial services and economic participation. The theory posits that intermediaries play a crucial role in mobilising savings, allocating capital efficiently, and providing risk management services that stimulate economic growth and poverty reduction (Gurley & Shaw, 1960). In the context of digital finance, fintech platforms, mobile money operators, and agent

banking systems function as modern financial intermediaries by leveraging digital technologies to reach underserved and financially excluded populations. By lowering costs, improving convenience, and overcoming geographical barriers, digital financial intermediaries expand financial access for vulnerable groups, enabling savings, credit access, and secure payment systems (Allen et al., 2019). Thus, Financial Intermediation Theory provides a strong theoretical foundation for assessing how digital finance can address poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

Hussaini and Umar Dikko (2025) investigated the impact of digital financial inclusion on poverty reduction in North-Western Nigeria using survey data from 415 households and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings revealed that digital financial inclusion significantly improved household welfare through enhanced income opportunities, increased purchasing power, and job creation. The study further established that access to digital financial services such as mobile money and digital banking reduces vulnerability to economic shocks among low-income households. This empirical evidence demonstrates that digital finance is a viable tool for poverty alleviation in Nigeria, with implications for vulnerable groups in urban areas such as Abuja.

Adefabi (2025) conducted a micro-level analysis of the relationship between digital financial inclusion and poverty reduction in Nigeria, focusing on household-level data. The study found that increased access to and usage of digital financial services were positively associated with improved welfare outcomes, including higher consumption levels and financial resilience. However, infrastructural deficits and institutional weaknesses were identified as constraints limiting the full benefits of digital finance. The study is relevant to the present research as it highlights that while digital finance can reduce poverty, supportive policies and infrastructure are necessary to ensure meaningful inclusion among vulnerable populations.

Mashoene and Schaling (2025) examined the effect of digital financial inclusion on inclusive growth and poverty reduction across emerging and developing economies using a System-Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) approach. Their results showed that digital financial inclusion significantly promotes inclusive economic growth, which in turn leads to reductions in poverty levels. Although the study adopted a cross-country perspective, its findings underscore the importance of digital finance as a driver of broad-based economic participation. This provides empirical justification for assessing how similar mechanisms may operate among vulnerable groups in Nigeria's urban context.

Abdullahi and Muhammad (2025) analysed the role of digital financial services in enhancing market access and economic participation in rural Northwestern Nigeria. The study revealed that mobile banking, fintech platforms, and point-of-sale services significantly improved access to credit, facilitated trade, and enhanced income-generating activities. These improvements contributed to reduced financial exclusion and increased economic resilience among underserved populations. The study's findings are relevant to the present research as they demonstrate how digital finance can empower marginalised groups, a dynamic that is equally applicable to vulnerable populations in Abuja.

Wale-Awe and Evans (2023) explored the relationship between digital financial inclusion, economic growth, inequality, and poverty in selected African countries using panel data analysis. The findings indicated that digital financial inclusion contributes to poverty reduction and income equality by expanding access to financial services and supporting inclusive growth. Although the study was conducted at a continental level, its conclusions provide strong empirical support for national-level investigations, such as the present study, which seeks to understand how digital finance can address poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria.

2.4 Research Gap

A critical review of the existing empirical literature reveals several gaps that justify the present study. Although studies such as Hussaini and Umar Dikko (2025) and Adefabi (2025) provide robust evidence on the poverty-reducing effects of digital financial inclusion in Nigeria, their analyses are

largely aggregated at regional or national levels and do not explicitly focus on the lived experiences of vulnerable groups within Nigeria's urban centres. Similarly, Abdullahi and Muhammad (2025) concentrate on rural contexts, leaving a gap in understanding how digital finance operates among urban vulnerable populations who face distinct socio-economic and institutional challenges. Moreover, cross-country and continental studies (Mashoene & Schaling, 2025; Wale-Awe & Evans, 2023), while valuable for generalisation, do not capture location-specific dynamics, behavioural factors, and structural constraints influencing digital finance adoption at the city level. Notably, none of the reviewed studies simultaneously examine digital finance, poverty, and financial exclusion within Abuja, Nigeria's capital city, where digital infrastructure coexists with significant socio-economic inequality. This study therefore fills this empirical gap by providing a context-specific assessment of the role of digital finance in addressing both poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, thereby contributing nuanced evidence to inform inclusive urban financial policies.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a mixed-methods research design, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches to examine how digital finance influences poverty reduction and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria. Quantitative data were generated through a structured questionnaire capturing access to digital financial services, literacy, income, and inclusion outcomes, while qualitative insights were obtained through key informant interviews with financial service providers, policymakers, and community leaders. The use of triangulation enhances the credibility and depth of findings by allowing cross-validation of results from multiple data sources (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

3.1.1 Study Area

The research was conducted in Abuja, Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory, a centrally located and purpose-built city established in 1991. Abuja's strategic geographic position, demographic diversity, and role as Nigeria's political and economic hub make it suitable for examining financial inclusion dynamics. Despite its relatively advanced infrastructure, the city exhibits a significant proportion of unbanked residents, reflecting persistent financial exclusion challenges (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2021). These characteristics provide a relevant context for assessing digital finance adoption among vulnerable populations.

3.1.2 Determination of Sample Size

The sample size was determined using the Yamane (1967) formula, which is appropriate for large populations and survey-based studies. Based on Abuja's estimated population and a 5% margin of error, a minimum sample size of 385 respondents was obtained. To improve reliability and account for non-response and incomplete questionnaires, the sample size was increased by 30%, a practice recommended for enhancing robustness and generalisability in social science research (Yamane, 1967).

3.1.3 Sampling Procedure

The target population comprised Abuja residents aged 18 years and above. A combination of probability and non-probability sampling techniques was employed. Stratified and simple random sampling supported representativeness across demographic groups, while purposive and snowball sampling facilitated access to vulnerable populations with limited visibility in formal databases. This approach ensured inclusiveness and adequate representation of both banked and unbanked individuals (Etikan et al., 2016).

3.1.4 Questionnaire Design

Data were collected using a 20-item structured questionnaire divided into sections covering barriers to digital finance adoption, poverty and financial inclusion outcomes, policy strategies, and demographic characteristics. The instrument employed Likert-scale, multiple-choice, and open-ended questions to capture both measurable indicators and contextual insights. This design enabled systematic assessment

of adoption constraints such as digital literacy, infrastructure, trust, and regulatory challenges (World Bank, 2022).

3.1.5 Identification of Participants

Participants were drawn from identified vulnerable groups, including low-income households, women, youth, and micro-entrepreneurs across selected communities in Abuja. Recruitment was facilitated through community centres, marketplaces, and partnerships with local NGOs and community-based organisations. This strategy enhanced access to hard-to-reach populations commonly excluded from formal financial systems (Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN], 2020).

3.1.6 Validity and Reliability Tests

Instrument validity was established through face, content, construct, and criterion validity, with content validity assessed using the Content Validity Index (CVI). Reliability was tested using the Kuder–Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20) to ensure internal consistency of dichotomous items. These procedures ensured that the instrument accurately and consistently measured key study variables (Taherdoost, 2016).

3.1.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants provided informed consent, confidentiality was maintained, and participation was voluntary with the option to withdraw at any stage. Special safeguards were applied when engaging vulnerable groups to prevent harm, exploitation, or coercion, consistent with international research ethics guidelines (World Bank, 2020).

3.2 Model Specification

The study adopts a binary logistic regression model, grounded in Financial Intermediation and Financial Inclusion Theory, to analyse the determinants of digital finance adoption and financial exclusion. Logistic regression is appropriate due to the binary nature of the dependent variable—financial inclusion status (included/excluded). The model estimates the probability of financial inclusion as a function of digital finance adoption, digital literacy, infrastructure access, trust, income, education, and regulatory barriers (Hosmer et al., 2013).

3.3 Measurement of Variables

Key variables were measured using both binary and continuous indicators. Financial exclusion and digital finance adoption were treated as binary variables, while poverty reduction, digital finance usage, and financial literacy were measured using continuous indices derived from income, employment, frequency of use, and knowledge scores. Demographic and socio-economic characteristics were included as control variables to isolate the net effects of digital finance adoption (OECD, 2020).

3.4 Nature and Sources of Data

The study relied primarily on quantitative primary data collected through surveys, complemented by qualitative interview data. Secondary data were sourced from reputable institutions such as the National Bureau of Statistics, Central Bank of Nigeria, World Bank, and International Monetary Fund to provide contextual and empirical support. This combination ensured data reliability, validity, and relevance (World Bank, 2022).

3.5 Estimation Technique

Data analysis was conducted using logistic regression estimated through maximum likelihood techniques. The method enables assessment of how explanatory variables influence the likelihood of financial inclusion while controlling for socio-economic and demographic factors. The results provide empirical evidence on the role of digital finance in reducing poverty and financial exclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja (Hosmer et al., 2013).

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

Table 4.1: Summary of Respondents' Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Mean	Min	Max	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis
Household Size	385	4.23	1	10	1.56	0.23	2.15
Household Income (₦)	385	250,000	50,000	1,000,000	200,000	1.15	3.00
Adoption of Digital Finance	385	0.72	0	1	0.45	-0.58	1.23
Limited Digital Literacy	385	0.41	0	1	0.45	0.21	1.56
Access to Internet & Mobile Network	385	0.85	0	1	0.35	-0.92	1.45
Perception of High Cost	385	0.51	0	1	0.50	0.15	1.23
Trust in Digital Finance Institutions	385	0.63	0	1	0.48	-0.35	1.21

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive characteristics of 385 sampled households. The average household size is approximately four persons, indicating moderately sized households with limited variability. Household income shows wide dispersion, reflecting income inequality among respondents, with a positively skewed distribution driven by a smaller proportion of high-income households. Digital finance adoption is relatively high, as nearly three-quarters of respondents reported using digital financial services, while a notable share still experiences limited digital literacy. Access to internet and mobile networks is widespread, suggesting infrastructural readiness, although cost perceptions and trust levels vary considerably. Overall, the table highlights demographic, economic, and digital readiness factors that are critical to understanding patterns of digital finance adoption and financial inclusion among households.

4.2 Results of Econometric Analysis

4.2.1 Household Adoption of Digital Finance

Table 4.1A: Logistic Regression Results for Household Adoption of Digital Finance (HADF)

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	-2.345	0.001
HH_DIGLIT	0.543	0.010
HH_INFRA	0.821	0.001
HH_INCOME	0.012	0.050
HH_EDU	0.351	0.010
HH_TRUST	0.928	0.001
HH_REGUL	-0.567	0.050

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1A shows that household adoption of digital finance is significantly influenced by digital literacy, infrastructure access, education, income, trust, and regulatory perception. The negative intercept suggests a low baseline probability of adoption in the absence of enabling factors. Digital literacy, infrastructure, education, and trust exhibit positive and statistically significant effects,

indicating that households with better skills, connectivity, knowledge, and confidence in institutions are more likely to adopt digital finance. Household income plays a marginal but significant role, while unfavorable perceptions of the regulatory environment reduce adoption. The model explains approximately 43.2% of the variation in adoption and demonstrates a good fit, confirming the relevance of the selected predictors.

Table 4.1B: Odds Ratios for Household Adoption of Digital Finance

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI
HH_DIGLIT	1.72	1.123–2.630
HH_INFRA	2.27	1.453–3.560
HH_INCOME	1.01	1.001–1.020
HH_EDU	1.42	1.073–1.881
HH_TRUST	2.54	1.743–3.690
HH_REGUL	0.57	0.342–0.940

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1B indicates that improved infrastructure and trust more than double the likelihood of digital finance adoption, while digital literacy and education also significantly enhance adoption odds. Income exerts only a minimal effect, reinforcing the inclusive nature of digital finance. Conversely, regulatory perception reduces adoption likelihood, suggesting possible concerns about compliance burdens or data security. The confidence intervals further confirm the robustness of infrastructure and trust as key drivers of adoption.

4.2.2 Barriers to Household Adoption of Digital Finance

Table 4.2A: Logistic Regression Results for Barriers to Household Adoption of Digital Finance (BHADF)

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	-2.512	0.001
HH_DIGLIT	0.482	0.010
HH_INFRA	0.753	0.001
HH_INCOME	0.015	0.050
HH_EDU	0.312	0.010
HH_TRUST	0.854	0.001
HH_REGUL	-0.592	0.050
HH_DIGLIT × HH_INFRA	0.275	0.010
HH_INCOME × HH_EDU	0.021	0.050

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2A reveals that digital literacy, infrastructure access, education, income, and trust significantly reduce barriers to digital finance adoption. Trust and infrastructure exert the strongest effects, while regulatory perception increases barriers, indicating potential concerns about restrictive policies. Interaction effects show that combined improvements in literacy and infrastructure, as well as income

and education, further lower barriers. The model explains 51.2% of the variance in adoption barriers and demonstrates satisfactory goodness of fit.

Table 4.2B: Odds Ratios for Barriers to Household Adoption of Digital Finance

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI
HH_DIGLIT	1.62	1.081–2.428
HH_INFRA	2.12	1.351–3.333
HH_INCOME	1.02	1.003–1.027
HH_EDU	1.37	1.034–1.803
HH_TRUST	2.35	1.615–3.410
HH_REGUL	0.54	0.324–0.940
HH_DIGLIT × HH_INFRA	1.32	1.053–1.646
HH_INCOME × HH_EDU	1.02	1.003–1.039

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2B confirms that trust and infrastructure substantially increase the likelihood of overcoming adoption barriers, while digital literacy and education provide moderate improvements. Regulatory perception remains a constraining factor. Interaction terms highlight the importance of integrated policy approaches that simultaneously address skills and infrastructure deficits.

4.2.3 Employment Model

Table 4.3: Employment Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	0.50	0.001
Digital Finance	0.20	0.010
HH_SIZE	-0.10	0.050
HH_AGE	0.05	0.100
HH_EDU	0.30	0.001
HH_LOCATION	0.20	0.010
VULNERABLE	-0.40	0.001

$R^2 = 0.28$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.25$ F-statistic = 8.56 (p = 0.001)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.3 indicates that digital finance and education positively influence employment outcomes, while vulnerability and household size reduce employment likelihood. Geographic location also matters, reflecting spatial disparities. Although the model explains a modest proportion of employment

variation, the overall significance confirms digital finance as an important facilitator of employment among households.

4.2.4 Access to Financial Services Model

Table 4.4: Access to Financial Services Model

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	0.80	0.001
Digital Finance	0.40	0.010
HH_SIZE	-0.20	0.100
HH_AGE	0.10	0.001
HH_EDU	0.50	0.010
HH_LOCATION	0.30	0.001
VULNERABLE	-0.60	0.001

$R^2 = 0.32$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.29$ F-statistic = 9.45 (p = 0.001)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.4 demonstrates that digital finance, education, age, and location significantly enhance access to financial services, while vulnerability reduces access. Education exhibits the strongest positive effect, emphasizing the role of human capital in financial inclusion. The model's explanatory power underscores the importance of combining digital finance initiatives with social and educational interventions.

4.2.5 Financial Exclusion Model

Table 4.5: Logistic Regression Results for Financial Exclusion

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Intercept	-2.51	0.001
Adoption	1.23	0.010
Limited Digital Literacy	0.85	0.050
Inflation	1.17	0.010
Healthcare	0.06	0.100
Lack of Trust	0.92	0.050
Regulatory Hindrance	1.31	0.010
Poverty Reduction	-0.15	0.100
Socioeconomic Status	-0.20	0.050
Geographic Location	0.75	0.050

$R^2 = 0.43$ Goodness-of-Fit p-value = 0.23

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.5 indicates that digital finance adoption, inflation, trust, regulatory barriers, and location significantly influence financial exclusion. While adoption improves inclusion, regulatory and trust-

related challenges increase exclusion risks. The model explains 43% of exclusion variation and fits the data well, highlighting the multidimensional nature of financial exclusion.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study demonstrate that digital finance plays a significant role in reducing poverty and enhancing financial inclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria. The results from the logistic regression models indicate that adoption of digital financial services such as mobile banking, fintech platforms, and electronic payment systems substantially improves access to financial services, employment opportunities, and household welfare. Consistent with Financial Intermediation Theory, digital finance reduces transaction costs and information asymmetries, thereby enabling households with limited income and education to participate more effectively in formal financial systems. These outcomes align with empirical evidence from prior studies that highlight digital finance as a catalyst for poverty reduction and inclusive growth in developing economies (Hussaini & Umar Dikko, 2025; Adefabi, 2025).

The study further reveals that digital literacy, access to reliable digital infrastructure, education, and institutional trust are critical determinants of digital finance adoption among vulnerable households. Households with higher levels of digital literacy and better internet or mobile network access were significantly more likely to adopt digital financial services and overcome barriers to financial inclusion. Conversely, regulatory constraints, low trust in financial institutions, and perceived high costs were found to impede adoption and deepen financial exclusion. These findings corroborate earlier research suggesting that while digital finance expands financial access, its effectiveness is contingent on supportive infrastructure, regulatory clarity, and consumer protection mechanisms (Wale-Awe & Evans, 2023; Mashoene & Schaling, 2025).

Finally, the analysis highlights persistent structural inequalities affecting vulnerable groups, including low-income households, women, youth, and informal-sector workers. Although digital finance positively influences employment and access to financial services, vulnerability status and geographic disparities continue to limit the full benefits of digital inclusion. The financial exclusion model indicates that macroeconomic pressures such as inflation, coupled with weak trust and regulatory barriers, exacerbate exclusion risks despite digital finance adoption. This suggests that digital finance alone is insufficient to eradicate poverty and exclusion without complementary social, educational, and economic policies. Overall, the findings underscore the need for an integrated policy framework that combines digital finance expansion with digital literacy programmes, consumer protection, and targeted poverty alleviation strategies to ensure inclusive and sustainable development in Abuja, Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study concludes that digital finance significantly contributes to reducing poverty and promoting financial inclusion among vulnerable groups in Abuja, Nigeria. The findings show that households with higher digital literacy, better access to internet and mobile networks, education, and trust in financial institutions are more likely to adopt digital financial services. Digital finance adoption positively influences access to financial services, employment opportunities, and overall household welfare. However, barriers such as perceived high costs, regulatory challenges, and the vulnerability of certain groups limit the full potential of digital financial inclusion. Thus, while digital finance is a powerful tool for poverty alleviation, its impact is moderated by socio-economic, infrastructural, and institutional factors.

Based on these findings, policymakers and stakeholders should prioritize expanding digital literacy programs, especially targeting low-income and vulnerable households, to enhance the adoption of digital finance. Investments in digital infrastructure, including internet and mobile network coverage, should be intensified to reduce access disparities. Financial institutions should also focus on building trust through transparency, consumer protection, and affordable service offerings. Additionally,

regulatory frameworks should balance oversight with innovation to prevent unintended barriers to adoption. Finally, complementary poverty alleviation measures, such as targeted financial education and social protection programs, should be integrated with digital finance initiatives to ensure inclusive and sustainable development in Abuja.

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